

Supplementary information on sensitivity runs

Sebastian Hinck

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The sensitivity runs documented here were conducted during the review process of

- Hinck, S., Gowan, E. J., Zhang, X., and Lohmann, G.: PISM-LakeCC: Implementing an adaptive proglacial lake boundary into an ice sheet model, *The Cryosphere Discuss.* [preprint], <https://doi.org/10.5194/tc-2020-353>, in review, 2020.

Table 1 provides an overview of all experiments. Further details on each run are given in the following sections. Snapshots of all experiments are appended at the end of this document.

1 Details on sensitivity runs

1.1 Default

The three default experiments (*lcc* - standard LakeCC, *lms* - LakeCC but strongly increased lacustrine calving to reduce ice shelf growth, and *ctrl* - no Lakes, no inland ocean due to use of SL2DCC model) described in the original manuscript were repeated, but with more output data.

1.2 Fill rate

Compared to the *lcc* experiment for these three experiments (*FR5*, *FR10* and *FR50*) only the option `max_fill_rate` was changed, which sets the rate at which the `lake_level` is gradually adjusted towards the `target_level`. Although the rates were drastically increased from the default value (5, 10, and 50m year⁻¹), the model stayed numerically stable. These experiments therefore are closer to the original assumption of lake basins being always filled. However, we want to state, that this is expected to be strongly dependent on the geometries of the ice and topography states that occur during the experiment. I.e. if the fill rate is set to a high value, it might happen that PISM runs into a state where a too rapid change in boundary conditions results in a model crash.

Table 1: List of all sensitivity experiments

Topic	short name	Description
Default	lcc	LakeCC
	lms	LakeCC, no shelf
	ctrl	SL2DCC
Fill rate	FR5	max_fill_rate set to 5m year ⁻¹
	FR10	max_fill_rate set to 10m year ⁻¹
	FR50	max_fill_rate set to 50m year ⁻¹
Earth model	GIA	Use of Earth model parameters for the Lingle-Clark bed deformation model similar to the parameters used for NAICE
	dtopg	To achieve better match with PD topography the initial LGM topography was adjusted
Melt rate	MR	To check the sensitivity on sub-shelf melting, melt rates were adjusted for lacustrine melt rates by setting a tuning parameter
Grounding line	TWO	Instead of slippery grounding line model the set_tillwat_ocean option was used
	nSG	Slippery grounding line model deactivated
Calving rate	redcalv	Reduced lacustrine calving by setting thickness threshold to 20m

1.3 Earth model

1.3.1 GIA

In this experiment, as suggested by Torsten Albrecht, we used parameters for the Earth model of the Lingle-Clark bed deformation model, that are closer to the parameters used by NAICE (Gowan et al., 2016). The viscosity of the upper mantle is set to $4 \cdot 10^{20}$ Pa s. Following (Bueler et al., 2007), from the 120km thick lithosphere the flexural rigidity of the lithosphere is calculated ($1.2627 \cdot 10^{25}$ Nm).

The results of this run are very similar to the *lcc* run. Small differences can only be seen in the geometry of the lake basins. Drainage of Lake Agassiz/Ojibway through Hudson Strait happens a bit earlier than in the *lcc* experiment.

1.3.2 dtopg

The PD topography of the *lcc* experiment strongly differs from the actual PD topography. This anomaly is added in this experiment to the LGM initial topography to result in a more realistic topography reconstruction.

The results, of course, show a much better fit to PD topography, but since big parts of the North American continent are much deeper depressed, during glacial retreat a giant ocean basin appears at the south-eastern ice margin. This prevents lakes from forming.

1.4 Melt rate

The sub-shelf melting is calculated based on the melt pump scheme by (Beckmann and Goosse, 2003). Although the parameters of the model were adapted for a marine setting around Antarctica, it was used in the previous experiments in the lacustrine setting without adaptation. In the *MR* experiment we apply a simple adaptation. Details are discussed in the following.

The melt flux is calculated as follows:

$$M = L^{-1} C \rho_{SW} c_p \gamma_{T,O} (T_O - T_f(S, d)) \quad (1)$$

Here, L is the latent heat of fusion, C is a tuning parameter, ρ_{SW} is the density of sea water, c_p is the heat capacity of the mixed layer, $\gamma_{T,O}$ is the thermal exchange velocity, T_O is the temperature of the ambient ocean and $T_f(S, d)$ the freezing temperature of water of salinity S at depth d . We rewrite this formula for lakes:

$$\begin{aligned} M &= L^{-1} C \rho_{FW} c_p \gamma_{T,L} (T_L - T_f(S_L, d)) \\ &= L^{-1} C C_\rho \rho_{SW} c_p C_\gamma \gamma_{T,O} C_T(T_O, T_L, S_L, d) (T_O - T_f(S, d)) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Here, T_L is the temperature of the lake, $\gamma_{T,L}$ is the thermal exchange velocity for a lake, and the C terms are factors to modify from lake to ocean parameterization.

- $C_\rho = \rho_{FW}/\rho_{SW}$ accounts for the difference in density. We neglect the density difference here and assume it is 1.
- $C_\gamma = \gamma_{T,L}/\gamma_{T,O}$:
This value is not easy to estimate. It describes how efficient heat is transported away in the boundary layer. The thermal exchange velocity γ_T is a function of the Nusselt number Nu of the mixed layer (Holland and Jenkins, 1999), which is proportional to the velocity of the mixed layer. We assume that this velocity depends on the density contrast between the melt water and the ambient water. In a marine environment the buoyancy of meltwater is about 200 times larger than in a lacustrine environment (Funk and Röthlisberger, 1989). We use this as our best guess: $C_\gamma = 200^{-1}$.
- $C_T = (T_L - T_f(S_L, d))/(T_O - T_f(S, d))$:
This term can not be expressed as a constant. It depends on the choices of the ambient ocean and lake temperatures, the ocean salinity and the depth. The marine values are set in the model: $S = 35\text{PSU}$ and $T_O = -1.7^\circ\text{C}$. Figure 1 shows C_T as a function of lake temperature for different depths. Even though the values vary a lot, we chose $C_T = 5$, which represents this value for $T_L = 2^\circ\text{C}$ and $d = 300\text{m}$.

With estimates for those values we can determine our tuning factor for lacustrine settings C^* :

$$C^* = C C_\rho C_\gamma C_T = 2.5 \cdot 10^{-4} \quad (3)$$

Figure 1: Dependence of C_T on the lake temperature for different depths.

Here we use $C = 0.01$, as in the experiments before.

Usage of this tuning factor strongly reduces the sub-shelf melting. When using this value, ice shelves in the marine environments grow excessively large. To prevent this, we apply the prescribed retreat parameterization, by setting the maximum extent of the ice sheet by defining a mask.

Even though the sub-shelf melting was strongly reduced, the ice retreat is nearly unchanged, as the calving parameterization governs the mass loss.

1.5 Grounding line

1.5.1 TWO

Instead of the slippery grounding line parameterization, the till-water ocean (<https://github.com/pism/pism/pull/425>) parameterization is used. As also found in Albrecht et al. (2020), the results are very similar to using the slippery grounding line treatment.

1.5.2 nSG

For this run the slippery grounding line treatment of PISM was disabled. This drastically reduces the transport of ice towards the marine and lacustrine bound-

aries. Due to the thicker grounded ice sheet the lake does not penetrate too far underneath the ice sheet. The breakup of LIS over Hudson Bay does not happen.

1.6 Calving rate

For the *redcalv* experiment the thickness calving threshold for lakes was reduced to 20m. Except for slightly larger ice shelves the results are the same as for the *lcc* run.

References

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2 Overview maps

Figure S1: Overview map at 500yr for the different experiments

Figure S2: Overview map at 1000yr for the different experiments

Figure S3: Overview map at 1500yr for the different experiments

Figure S4: Overview map at 2000yr for the different experiments

Figure S5: Overview map at 2500yr for the different experiments

Figure S6: Overview map at 3000yr for the different experiments

Figure S7: Overview map at 3500yr for the different experiments

Figure S8: Overview map at 4000yr for the different experiments

Figure S9: Overview map at 4500yr for the different experiments

Figure S10: Overview map at 5000yr for the different experiments

Figure S11: Overview map at 5500yr for the different experiments

Figure S12: Overview map at 6000yr for the different experiments

Figure S13: Overview map at 6500yr for the different experiments

Figure S14: Overview map at 7000yr for the different experiments

Figure S15: Overview map at 7500yr for the different experiments

Figure S16: Overview map at 8000yr for the different experiments

Figure S17: Overview map at 8500yr for the different experiments

Figure S18: Overview map at 9000yr for the different experiments

Figure S19: Overview map at 9500yr for the different experiments

Figure S20: Overview map at 10000yr for the different experiments

Figure S21: Overview map at 10500yr for the different experiments

Figure S22: Overview map at 11000yr for the different experiments

Figure S23: Overview map at 11500yr for the different experiments

Figure S24: Overview map at 12000yr for the different experiments

Figure S25: Overview map at 12500yr for the different experiments

Figure S26: Overview map at 13000yr for the different experiments

Figure S27: Overview map at 13500yr for the different experiments

Figure S28: Overview map at 14000yr for the different experiments

Figure S29: Overview map at 14500yr for the different experiments

Figure S30: Overview map at 15000yr for the different experiments

Figure S31: Overview map at 15500yr for the different experiments

Figure S32: Overview map at 16000yr for the different experiments

Figure S33: Overview map at 16500yr for the different experiments

Figure S34: Overview map at 17000yr for the different experiments

Figure S35: Overview map at 17500yr for the different experiments

Figure S36: Overview map at 18000yr for the different experiments

Figure S37: Overview map at 18500yr for the different experiments

Figure S38: Overview map at 19000yr for the different experiments

Figure S39: Overview map at 19500yr for the different experiments

Figure S40: Overview map at 20000yr for the different experiments

Figure S41: Overview map at 20500yr for the different experiments

Figure S42: Overview map at 21000yr for the different experiments

Figure S43: Overview map at 21500yr for the different experiments

Figure S44: Overview map at 22000yr for the different experiments

Figure S45: Overview map at 22500yr for the different experiments

Figure S46: Overview map at 23000yr for the different experiments

Figure S47: Overview map at 23500yr for the different experiments

Figure S48: Overview map at 24000yr for the different experiments

Figure S49: Overview map at 24500yr for the different experiments

Figure S50: Overview map at 25000yr for the different experiments

Figure S51: Overview map at 25500yr for the different experiments

Figure S52: Overview map at 26000yr for the different experiments